

male sterile (CMS) lines. Two indices were used: (1) pollen morphology and staining pattern and (2) type of interaction with a set of maintainers and restorers of wild abortive (WA) cyto sterile stock. The newly developed CMS lines are grouped using these indices as follows: I. RPMS1 (*O. rufipogon*; VNI) and RPMS2 (*O. nivara*; DRW21039) are gametophytic types; II. RPMS3 (*O. nivara*; DRW21030) is similar to MS577A in pollen stainability, but the restoration and maintenance reactions are similar to those of

the WA type; III. RPMS4 (*O. nivara*; DRW21018) is a sporophytic type, but restorers and maintainers are different from WA; IV. RPMS5 and RPMS6 (*O. nivara*; RPW21111) are sporophytic types with restorer and maintainer reactions similar to those of WA. All the new CMS lines possessed complete panicle exertion essential for enhancing outcrossed seed yield.

For the two stable CMS lines, MS577A and IR66707A, no restorers are available in cultivated rice germplasm. A search for restorer sources for these

CMS lines was made among the wild accessions of the A genome species. Although none of the accessions could restore fertility in IR66707A, three accessions of *O. rufipogon* (VN2, DRW22016, DRW220175) and one each from *O. sativa* f. *spontanea* (RPW20001) and *O. glaberrima* (DRGL 30090) did restore fertility in MS577A. Studies on the genetics of fertility restoration in these cross combinations indicated that two dominant genes act in an additive manner to restore fertility. ■

Krishna CMS lines in the background of four different cytoplasmic sources in rice

S. B. Pradhan and P. J. Jachuck, Central Rice Research Institute, Cuttack 753006, India

Four cytoplasmic male sterile (CMS) lines of Krishna with sterile cytoplasm from four different sources (wild abortive [WA], *O. perennis*, Kalinga 1, and Lalruma from Mizoram) have been developed. The two CMS lines—Krishna A with WA and Krishna A with *O. perennis* as a source—were developed through conversion with CMS lines V20A (WA) and IR66707A (*O. perennis*), respectively, by subsequent backcrossing with common isonuclear main-

tainer Krishna A. But Krishna A with Kalinga 1 and Krishna A with Lalruma cytoplasmic sources were developed through indica / indica crosses. These four CMS lines are all dwarf in stature, are of medium duration, and have reduced white anthers that exhibit 80-90% unstained withered pollen grains.

To understand the nature of these four cyto sterility sources, they were testcrossed with four maintainers—V20B (maintainer of WA), IR66707B (maintainer of *O. perennis*), Yar-Ai-ZhaoB (maintainer of Gambiaca), and MS577B (maintainer of *O. sativa* f. *spontanea*)—and the elite inbred lines SPR7210-1-3, IR48725-B-B-120-1, NDR30074, TTB150-61, and R657-93-869. The sterility of the four CMS lines was maintained by the four main-

tainers. The restorer SPR7210-1-3 of Krishna A (WA) was found to be a maintainer of the other three CMS lines—Krishna A (*O. perennis*), Krishna A (Kalinga 1), and Krishna A (Lalruma)—whereas the restorer IR48725-B-B-120-1 of Krishna A (WA) behaved as partial restorer of Krishna A (Kalinga 1) and Krishna A (Lalruma) and as a maintainer of Krishna A (*O. perennis*). Variety R657-93-869 was found to be a partial restorer of Krishna A (WA) and Krishna A (Lalruma) and a maintainer of Krishna A (Kalinga 1) and Krishna A (*O. perennis*). The restorer TTB150-61 for Krishna A (Lalruma) behaved as a partial restorer of Krishna A (WA) and Krishna A (Kalinga 1), and as a maintainer of Krishna A (*O. perennis*). ■

Characterizing thermo-sensitive genic male sterile lines of rice

B. C. Viraktamath, M. T. Lopez, and S. S. Virmani, IRRI

The cytoplasmic male sterility (CMS) system is widely used to develop rice hybrids. Although effective, this system is quite cumbersome to practice. Certain genic male sterile lines that revert to fertility under specific temperature are called thermosensitive genic male sterile (TGMS) lines. Deployment of the TGMS system to develop two-line hybrids has several

advantages over the conventional CMS system, as it requires neither maintainers for seed multiplication nor restorers for producing hybrids. In addition, two-line hybrids may not suffer from possible negative effects of the sterility-inducing cytoplasm. For an effective use of TGMS lines, they have to be characterized for their critical sterility and fertility points. This information is essential for deciding on a suitable location and / or period for seed multiplication and hybrid seed production. Two IRRI-bred indica TGMS lines-IR68945-4-33-4-14 and IR68949-11-5-31-along with their japonica TGMS donor, were charac-

terized under controlled conditions in the IRRI phytotron. These lines were subjected to eight constant temperatures (20-32 °C) and four day-night combination temperatures (27 / 21 °C-32 / 24 °C) for a period of 3 wk during the sensitive stage. The critical sterility point for both lines was 30 °C and above, whereas it was only 27 °C and above for Norin PL 12. The critical fertility points for the indica TGMS lines ranged between 24-28 °C (constant temperate) and 27 / 21 °C-28 / 22 °C (day-night combination temperature). Norin PL 12 was found to be very sensitive to higher temperature compared with the indica TGMS lines.

Comparative effects from treatments revealed that the maximum temperature in day-night combination temperatures was crucial in determining the sterility or fertility of TGMS lines. The effects of intervening fertility-inducing temperature (27 °C) during the sterility phase (32/24 °C) were studied in TGMS lines IR68945-4-33-4-14, ID24, and Norin PL 12. Even an exposure for 2 h at 27 °C could induce fertility in IR68945-4-33-4-14, whereas ID24 remained unaffected even after 10 h exposure at 27 °C. The behavior of Norin PL 12 was intermediate in this respect as 4 h of interruption could induce fertility. ■

Identifying and characterizing thermosensitive cytoplasmic male sterile lines

A. J. Ali, Crop Improvement Department, Agriculture College and Research Institute, Navalur Kuttapattu, Trichy 620009; E. A. Siddiq, Indian Council of Agricultural Research, New Delhi 110001; F. U. Zaman, Indian Agricultural Research Institute, New Delhi 110012; and M. I. Ahmed, Directorate of Rice Research, Hyderabad 500030, India

In wheat, an alloplasmic line of Norin 26 (*Triticum aestivum*) with *Aegilops crassa* cytoplasm has been found to show male sterility under long-day (15.0 h) conditions and fertility under short-day (14.5 h) conditions with no influence of temperature. In the present study, a similar influence of temperature rather than photoperiod was observed in wild abortive (WA) cytoplasmic male sterile (CMS) line J24A (Pusa 33-16A). It was studied along with its maintainer line J24B (Pusa 33-16B) under different temperature regimes for fertility-sterility alterations. The pattern of their fertility-sterility transformation revealed them to be of high critical sterility point (CSP) and high critical fertility point (CFP) type. Yet they differed in their degree of transformation; the CSP was 33.8 °C in J24A and 35.1 °C in J24B. Although the

CFPs of both fall in the same range (24–28 °C), a comparative study of the A and B lines for their temperature-influenced sterility-fertility behavior revealed the thermosensitive genic male sterility (TGMS) gene to be probably linked to the nuclear sterility gene (*rf*). Fertile cytoplasm (C gene) also possessed some degree of influence on fertility as well as on TGMS genes located in the nuclear genome. This was evident from the B line, which showed a relatively higher CSP and CFP than the A line. To have a stable CMS line, the nuclear genome should have the fertility gene *Rf* with the environment-sensitive male sterility gene (EGMS) in a dominant state, so that neither temperature nor daylength would affect its stability for pollen sterility. A CMS line having the

EGMS gene in a recessive state can be deployed under high-temperature conditions for hybrid seed production. The A line in this state will be more stable for sterility because of the combined effect of both fertility and EGMS genes. Seed multiplication of the CMS line can be done with ease, taking advantage of fertility transformation under low-temperature conditions. To minimize the risk of temperature fluctuations, the CMS line can be planted in alternate rows with its B line. If high temperatures prevail during the seed multiplication phase and make the CMS line completely sterile, the B line as a maintainer can provide abundant pollen for outcrossing. If selfing does occur, it would help to further increase seed yield of the thermosensitive CMS line. ■

Screening rice germplasm for floral attributes that influence outcrossing

S. K. Sahoo, R. Singh, L. C. Prasad, R. M. Singh, D. K. Singh, Genetics and Plant Breeding Department, Institute of Agricultural Sciences, Banaras Hindu University, Varanasi 221005; and S. K. Agrawal, Directorate of Rice Research, Rajendranagar, Hyderabad 500030, India

A cytosterile line with high outcrossing potential would economize the cost of hybrid seed production in rice. We screened rice germplasm to identify genotypes with useful floral traits that could influence outcrossing. We used prospective maintainers and restorers in a testcross nursery program. Isolation of prospective maintainers with useful floral characteristics could lead to the development of cytosterile lines with high outcrossing potential

through a backcrossing program. We evaluated 75 genotypes for floral and related traits: duration of opening of florets, angle of opened florets, percentage of exerted stigma, spikelet length, anther length, stigma length, panicle length, number of effective tillers plant⁻¹, grain yield plant⁻¹, and plant height. The analysis of variance recorded highly significant differences for all the traits, indicating the presence of a sufficient degree of variation for these traits for selection among cultivars. We identified genotypes Aditya, VL Dhan 63, IET10119, IET10115, IET10119, Shankar, VL Dhan 8, Pratibha, Kunti, Surajmukhi, and Vikas as possessing multiple floral traits that would enhance seed set. All these genotypes can therefore be used as parental lines to develop hybrids and enhance outcrossing. ■

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